

Participatory tools

GROUP WORK (ONLINE OR NOT)

EMBEDDING THE METHODS AND TOOLS CO-DESIGNED BY THE INNOVATION PARTNERSHIP ENSURING OWNERSHIP

How to ensure 'ownership' of results (who can use what? How to share?)

It is helpful to plan to involve users from the beginning and maintain a link throughout the project.

Once the deliverable is produced, you should communicate to a wide circle of end-users (among others) who are not aware of the results. The end-users need to take ownership of the outputs and make them as useful as possible. This involves different steps:

- Make it easy to understand the outcomes,
- Emphasize the benefits to users,
- Support adaptation if necessary.

How to solve it

The results need to be accessible. The communication needs to be adapted to user types (the form and the language).

You can encourage "understanding by doing" and engage the actors using the tool in the production.

Do not hesitate to leave room for adaptation and consider users' needs, expectations, and constraints.

Word of advice

Remember that adaptations may be necessary to facilitate use and stay flexible (as much as possible).

One example of a tool to facilitate this stage

Group work (online or not) - Abolish the distance. Increase the frequency.

Description of the tool

- **What:** getting participants to work together on a given issue, taking advantage of the richness of the exchanges and the diversity of points of view, facilitating the expression of participants who are uncomfortable in a large group
- **How long:** depend on the objective, from 10' to 45'
- **How many:** from 2 to 6 per group
- **What you'll need:** something for the group to take notes,
 - Face to face: flip chart paper, coloured markers
 - Online: tools like Klaxoon, MURAL, etc.

LIAISON Interactive guide to facilitating participatory projects

Steps:

- The facilitator gives the instructions, making sure that they are clear to everyone. The time available for group work should also be clear to all
- For the creation of groups, several solutions are possible:
 - Prepare them in advance if you wish to ensure a particular mix of participants, such as if you group them according to specific themes for different participants (by sector, for example)
 - Let the participants form them at will
 - Make them random. For example, if you want three groups, designate each participant by number: 1, 2, 3, 1, 2, 3...
- Give each group something to take notes on to report back later. At the beginning of the group work, the facilitator or group can choose who will share the summary with the rest of the large group (one or more people).
- While the groups are working, the facilitator can answer questions and drop in on the different groups to help/clarify if needed and check on progress. The facilitator is the timekeeper.
- When finished, participants come back together and share their thoughts with the whole group. This can be done in different ways:
 - Each group presents what they have discussed,
 - Each group gives one or a few key points,
 - The first group present and the others complete.

Tips:

- Face to face:
 - Do not hesitate to give the instructions orally, write them down and ask if they are clear to everyone
 - Inform participants when they are close to the end of the time allocated to allow them to keep time for synthesis and writing if necessary
 - Avoid letting participants do their groups on their own if they don't know each other to save time
 - If several group work sessions are planned, if the objective allows, change the groups so that participants work with different people
- Online:
 - Concerning the tools:
 - Not too many different tools in the meeting
 - Train yourself
 - Practice! Test the tools before the meeting
 - Use tools that you know well
 - Have the user profile in mind to know whether they are used to doing it or not
- For the facilitator:
 - Start small so that people take ownership of the tools
 - Work in pairs to facilitate
 - Prepare (takes time)
- Logistic:
 - Distribute user / participant tutorials
 - Keep to a short time frame

